

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR OF GFRP/CONCRETE COMPOSITE SLAB

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a composite slab is proposed with steel fiber reinforced self-compacting concrete and a corrugated glass fiber reinforced polymer deck, serving as permanent formwork and providing tensile reinforcement. A preliminary experimental investigation was conducted to evaluate its behavior with a four-point bending test in a 1800mm clear span. The initial detachment of the GFRP deck was the first stage of failure by longitudinal shear, reducing stiffness by initiating a relative slip, which resulted in a decrease of load capacity. The slab withstood a bending moment of 13.80 kN.m in the initial detachment and 21.73 kN.m at flexural failure, exhibiting a pseudo-ductile performance because its displacements until the end of the test.

KEYWORDS

FRP reinforced concrete structures, composite structures, composite concrete GFRP slab, GFRP deck, FRP structure.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have the potential to widely replace the use of steel and aluminum, often with superior performance. Substituting steel components with composites can result in a weight reduction of 60 to 80% of the structure, while the use of composites instead of aluminum can achieve a weight reduction of 20 to 50%. (Mazumdar, 2002). Among the models with composite structures with FRP, the Stay-In-Place (SIP) formwork system stands out, in which the FRP sheet itself serves as reinforcement for concrete and as a permanent formwork, reducing formwork costs, with or without the need for shoring.

According to Nelson et al. (2014), the most commonly used geometries in stay-in-place composite slabs are: slabs with T-shaped stiffeners (Figure 1 a), plates reinforced with hollow section profiles (Figure 1 b), grids adhered to the plate (Figure 1 c), ribbed plates (Figure 1 d), double cavity system (Figure 1 e), and corrugated plates (Figure 1 f).

Figure 1 - Commonly used geometries in stay-in-place composite slabs. Source: Nelson et al. (2014).

In addition to the aforementioned benefits, Pornasiri et al (2022) highlights that the incorporation of structurally integrated Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) SIP formworks enhances the load-

carrying capacity of the decks. The presence of these formworks enables the occurrence of the first crack at a higher loading level, thanks to the efficient transfer of stress from the concrete to the GFRP SIP formwork.

Zuo et al. (2018), Tian et al. (2018), and Nelson & Fam (2013) conducted research on straight GFRP deck forms with stiffeners as bottom reinforcement, utilizing steel bars and GFRP bars for top reinforcement. Conversely, studies such as Fam & Nelson (2012) and He et al. (2012) examined corrugated GFRP deck forms as bottom reinforcement, along with GFRP steel bars as top reinforcement. The use of bars as reinforcement was not employed in studies such as Fang et al. (2016), who investigated a straight form with stiffeners using only conventional concrete, and Mastali et al. (2014), who studied sandwich slabs with fiberglass plates and steel fiber-reinforced concrete. As a result, this study distinguishes itself from existing literature by introducing an innovative approach: a composite slab that incorporates a corrugated GFRP deck and Steel Fiber Reinforced Self-Compacting Concrete (SFRSCC) without the requirement of additional bars on the upper surface. Another noteworthy aspect pertains to the treatment of the interface. While the prevailing practice documented in the literature involves bonding the sand layer with epoxy adhesive, this research employs the manufacturing resin itself for this purpose. These modifications aim to optimize the efficiency of the slab construction process without compromising its structural performance.

To assess the feasibility of conducting a more extensive investigation based on the proposed approach, an initial experiment was conducted with a single specimen. The primary objective of this preliminary phase was to gain initial insights and determine whether it would be worthwhile to proceed with a more comprehensive study.

PROPOSED COMPOSITE SLAB

The object of this paper is a composite slab made of SFRSCC and a corrugated deck of GFRP for residential applications (Figure 2), using the composite as a permanent formwork and as the slab tensile reinforcement. The slab has a length of 1,900 mm and a width of 536 mm, simply supported at the ends, with a span length of 1,800 mm and a GFRP deck with a 5.28 mm thickness.

Figure 2 - Composite slabs researched.

The incorporation of high modulus of elasticity fibers in the cementitious matrix has as its main purpose the increase of tensile strength and ductility of the concrete. This addition does not significantly alter the ultimate compressive strength, but ductile behavior is desirable in the mixed slab to avoid brittle failure in the hardened state when there is no additional reinforcement present.

According to Pereira (2017), steel fibers are more advantageous than welded mesh in volumetric fractions smaller than 1%, as they help reduce cracking due to shrinkage, distribute loads more efficiently due to their random configuration, directly reduce labor costs, and are less susceptible to corrosion than longitudinal reinforcement. Furthermore, according to Ahmad (2020), the inclusion of steel fibers in concrete reduces crack propagation, thereby optimizing durability aspects such as water absorption, acid resistance, and permeability.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM OF COMPOSITE SLAB

GFRP deck design and production

The composite slab was designed based on recommendations by Souza & Lameiras (2023), for residential use. It was designed to withstand a live load of 1.5 kN/m² and a dead load of 3.97 kN/m², excluding the weight of the GFRP deck, with a maximum deflection of 7.2 mm, complying with a 1/250 span ratio.

The GFRP deck were manufactured at the University of Brasilia using Vacuum-Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM), with a system created by Silva (2020) and adapted for creating the deck. The manufacturing process assembly followed the sequence shown in Figure 3, and it was composed of eight layers of 700 g/m² unidirectional “R” glass fibers, two layers of 450 g/m² glass Chopped Strand Mat (CSM). For every 1 g of fiberglass, 1 g of polyester resin, 0.1 g of styrene monomer, and 0.001 g of MEK catalyst were used.

After production, tests were conducted to determine the tensile strength of the composites. To ensure strong connection between elements, the deck was coated with sand to improve its adherence to wet concrete by promoting internal roughness.

Figure 3 - Vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding assembly.

The composites were mechanically characterized by extracting five random specimens measuring 25 cm × 1.5 cm, with orientations of 0° and 90°, to determine the ultimate tensile strength. The tests were conducted at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory of the University of Brasília, following the ASTM 3039M standard - Tensile Testing of Polymer Matrix Composites (2017), using the "810 Material Test System" press from MTS brand with a 100 kN load cell capacity. The specimens were clamped at their ends using a compressed air pressure system and subjected to a tensile load at a speed of 2 mm/min. The axial displacement was measured using an extensometer, up to approximately 50% of its load capacity due to the brittle behavior of the material. Since the composite behaved linearly elastic until failure, a linear progression was used to estimate the modulus of elasticity.

Material properties of GFRP

The in-plane Tensile Properties of the composite material was tested according to ASTM D3039 (ASTM, 2017). The averaged tensile strength and modulus is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Tensile properties of the composite materials

Deck Code	Glass Fibers (kg/m ²)		Tensile Strength (MPa)		Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)
	Continuous	CSM	0°	90°	0°
D8F	5.6	0.90	555.71 ¹ ± 56.58	105.55 ± 8.25	34.18 ± 1.52

¹ It's the tensile strength obtained, although occurred relative slip at the test. The estimated tensile strength is 778.40 MPa according through other tested laminates.

Composite slab production

After fabrication, the trapezoidal panels were cleaned and treated with a new layer of undiluted resin. Sand was applied to the surface of the resin within its pot life period by sieving it through a mesh sieve with a mesh with opening of 2.18 mm. This treatment aimed to optimize the bond performance between the concrete and the GFRP sheet. After the resin curing period, any excess sand on the panel was removed using a plastic bristle broom to ensure no loose particles remained on the surface.

The concrete used in the mixed slab was a SFRSCC previous used in research conducted by Cardoso (2020) at the Graduate Program in Structures and Civil Construction at UnB and adapted to this research. It was produced one batch of concrete for the slab and the mix proportion used was 1:1.16:1.56:0.46 (cement:sand:aggregate:water) with the addition of 0.6% of ST-33/60 steel fibers with a diameter (d_f) of 0.55 mm, length (l_f) of 33 mm, aspect ratio (l_f/d_f) of 60, and tensile strength of 1100 MPa; 7.375% of limestone filler and 0.04% of superplasticizer additive. The flow spread of concretes in the fresh state was registered following the recommendations of NBR 15823 (ABNT 2017) and the average value obtained for the slump-flow of SFRSCC was equal to 61 mm. To determine their mechanical properties, axial compression tests were conducted using cylindrical specimens according to NBR 5739 (ABNT, 2018).

Material properties of Concrete

The compressive strength (f_{ck}) of concretes were determined according to NBR 5739 (ABNT, 2018) with three cylinders of 100 mm diameter and 200 mm height. The cylinders was prepared and moist cured for 35 days inside a chamber with humidity control under the laboratory temperature . The compressive test was performed using a EMIC press, servo-controlled hydraulic-system. The tests were controlled by the internal displacement transducer of the test machine at a rate of 0.1 mm/min and the average measured of compressive strength was $20,05 \text{ MPa} \pm 1,11 \text{ MPa}$.

Test set-up and instrumentation

The main objective of the setup was to determine the behavior of the composite slab under bending. To achieve this, a four-point bending test was conducted, incorporating adaptations from Eurocode 4 (2004) for composite steel slabs. Figure 4 illustrates the set-up configuration, which involved a span of 1800 mm with loads applied at 1/4 of the span.

Figure 4 - Four-point bending test set-up.

Deformations were measured using strain gauges at the mid-span and at the load application point, located at 1/4 of the support span, as indicated in Figure 5. To measure the slip between the GFRP deck and the concrete, LVDTs (Linear Variable Differential Transformers) from HBM with a 50 mm cursor and a precision of 0.01 mm were positioned at the ends. Additionally, LVDTs were placed on the outer side to measure displacement at the center and in the region of the load application. This allowed for

the consideration of displacements in both the concrete and GFRP deck. Figure 5 shows the instrumentation scheme.

Figure 5 – Four-point bending test instrumentation scheme.

For the loading process, a single hydraulic cylinder from ENERPAC was used to apply the load vertically, from top to bottom. The applied load was monitored using a KRATOS load cell with a capacity of 500 kN. Data acquisition was performed continuously using the Spider 8 data acquisition system, manufactured by HBM. The acquired data was processed and stored using the CATMAN computer program. The sampling frequency for data recording was set at 1 Hz, equivalent to one reading per second. The measured load value was subsequently adjusted to account for the self-weight of the slab and equipment.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Failure Mode of composite slab

The first behavior observed in the composite slab was a longitudinal crack in the region between the GFRP deck and the concrete (Figure 6a) at an initial load of 50.45 kN, with no changes in overall stiffness or load capacity. As the loading continued, the deformation and initial detachment of the side flanges of the deck became noticeable (Figure 6b), with an initial displacement of 4.26 mm located at MID axis with a 61.34 kN applied load and a displacement of 7.32 mm in the SUP axis with a 66.67 kN applied load.

Despite the displacement at the edges of the slab, it continued to exhibit a high load capacity with the displacements increased almost linearly with the applied load, experiencing slight decreases as the lateral sliding and detachment of the deck occurred.

In the concrete, shear cracks were initially observed in the load application region, followed by flexural cracks along midspan. However, it is important to note that internal cracks in the tensile region could not be visually identified until the deck detachment due to the SIP formwork configuration.

Relative slip of the deck was observed at both ends of the slab, and its final configuration can be seen in Figure 6c. After completing the test, regions were observed where the sand was fully adhered to the concrete (Figure 6d), as well as regions where the sand was adhered to the deck, indicating the presence of an effective bond between the analyzed materials.

The final failure mode of the specimen is shown at Figure 6e and Figure 6f. It includes SFRSCC cracking without breaking the fiber or its anchorage in flexure and bending rupture of the GFRP deck. It was observed cracks in the load application axis due to flexural stress and after the complete detachment of the GFRP deck, it was observed flexural cracks due to tensile stress at the midspan, those cracks could not be visually verified earlier because of the SIP form deck.

(a) Initial crack at concrete x deck interface

(b) Initial detachment

(c) Relative slip of the GFRP deck

(d) Sand coated configuration

(e) Bending failure - Front

(f) Bending failure - Back

Figure 6 – Composite slab behavior until failure.

A series of behaviors led to the observed failure, beginning with the gradual detachment of the GFRP deck, which decreased the specimen's stiffness and ultimately resulted in the maximum support capacity being reached due to flexural failure of the GFRP deck at the midspan with 96.58 kN load.

Similar behavior was observed by Honickman (2008) in his research on 400 mm slabs composed of concrete and straight GFRP plate, which exhibited a horizontal debonding crack along the concrete x plate interface, flexural cracks, relative slip, and ultimate failure due to plate detachment in specimens with sand coating for spans of 1000 mm and 2200 mm.

In their research on GFRP ribbed panels, Nelson & Fam (2013) observed a series of behaviors that led to a progressive failure, characterized by three stages. Initially, the panel-to-panel lap splices started to peel. Subsequently, the specimens experienced a punching shear failure, exhibiting increased reserve capacity and significant pseudoductility. Finally, after the adhesive peeled at the lap splice, the fasteners began to tilt and tear through the GFRP panels, resulting in a bearing failure mode.

The variation in failure modes among composite slabs highlights the importance of studying their behaviors, variations, and capacities for different geometries, as well as various forms of connections.

These factors directly influence the final behavior of the specimen and should be taken into account in determining the load-carrying capacity.

Load-deflection relationship

Figure 7 shows the load-displacement performance of the composite slab specimen. The displacement are reported at MID axis (Figure 7a) and at the SUP axis (Figure 7b), and it was compared the performance of concrete with the GFRP deck.

Figure 7 - Load x displacement relationship.

The deck detachment began at 63.52% of the ultimate load, indicating a considerable load reserve in the composite structure until reaching its final capacity.

The ultimate capacity of the slab was reached by flexural failure of the GFRP deck after successive detachment of the deck, starting from the external longitudinal flanges towards the internal rib. The concrete fiber composite slab with GFRP deck withstood a load of 96.58 kN with a maximum deflection measured by the installed LVDTs of 36.97 mm. Despite exhibiting linear behavior, the structure showed significant deflections and structural noises, resulting in a pseudo-ductile failure performance.

Composite action and relative slip

The bond between the FRP deck and the concrete is extremely important for achieving composite behavior between the elements. As shown in Figure 8a, monitoring the relative slip between the deck and the concrete revealed a maximum slip of 24,39 mm on the right side of the specimen.

The measured composite behavior of the composite slab can be divided into four stages after the appearance of the longitudinal crack following the initial load application, as illustrated in Figure 8b:

- (S1) - Stage 1: Partial detachment of the longitudinal side edges of the slab at midspan, caused by a load of 61.37 kN.
- (S2) - Stage 2: Partial detachment of the longitudinal side edges of the slab at SUP axis, with a load of 66.67 kN.
- (S3) - Stage 3: Maximum displacement measured by the LVDT of the GFRP deck at a load of 86.21 kN, with a maximum displacement difference of 13.74 mm at the SUP axis, compared to the concrete.
- (S4) - Stage 4: Maximum displacement measured by the LVDT of the concrete at a 88.35 kN load.

(A) Relative slip of GFRP deck (B) Displacement x span relationship
 Figure 8 - Composite action of composite deck.

After those four stages, the displacements of the composite slab exceeded the capacity of the LVDTs, and it became to show significant differences in displacement between the GFRP deck and the concrete. This led to to parcial detachments until flexural failure.

Strain results

The strain distributions at MID axis (midspan) and LS axis are presented in Figure 9. The strain increased with increasing load, with some slightly decrescing of load capacity at MID axis and LS axis detachment, indicating an almost linearly behaviour until failure.

(a) Strain at the center axis (b) Stran at Ls axis
 Figure 9 - Load x strain relationship composite slab.

As depicted in Figure 9, the top rib of the deck underwent compression up to approximately 91% of its load-bearing capacity. Towards the end of the bending test, a loss of stiffness caused the position of the neutral axis to shift upwards, resulting in tensile stress at the top of the rib. This led to a completely

tensile-loaded cross-section of the GFRP deck. At the maximum load the strain of concrete reached $-944 \mu\text{m/m}$ and $8248,91 \mu\text{m/m}$ for the deck.

Analysis of flexural capacity

The main objective of the presented composite slab was to withstand a bending moment of 1.65 kN.m with an acceptable maximum deflection of 7.2 mm . According to the results, it is evident that the slab exceeded expectations for the intended use, withstanding a bending moment of 13.8 kN.m at the initial detachment of the sheet, resulting in a deflection $59,17\%$ lower than the maximum deflection. It ultimately reached a maximum bending moment of 21.73 kN.m. , which demonstrates the feasibility of producing a larger quantity of specimens for the study of composite slabs with deck, allowing for further investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the flexural behavior of GFRP/concrete composite slab with SFRSCC and a corrugated GFRP deck. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this experimental study:

- (1) The structural performance of the slab is initially governed by the composite action between the deck and the concrete, resulting from longitudinal shear. After detachment, the investigated specimen exhibited a pseudo-ductile behavior with significant deflections until failure.
- (2) The detachment of the sheet began at 63.52% of the ultimate load, indicating a considerable load reserve in the composite structure until reaching its final capacity.
- (3) The use of fiber-reinforced concrete proved to be suitable for the intended purpose.
- (4) The surface treatment demonstrated effectiveness in promoting composite action between the materials; however, it can be further optimized to prevent or even increase the sheet detachment load.
- (5) The studied specimen failed due to flexural stress in the area of the FRP sheet, with a load of 96.58 kN .
- (6) The maximum relative slip between the deck and the concrete was $24,39 \text{ mm}$.
- (7) During the bending test, the top rib of the deck experienced compression up to approximately 91% of its load-bearing capacity. The deflection and formation of cracks, caused by the applied load, led to a reduction in stiffness and resulted in tensile stress at the top of the rib towards the end of the test.
- (8) The data demonstrates viability in conducting a more extensive investigation based on the proposed approach, including those with thinner decks. It allows for exploring lower reinforcement ratios of the slab, considering the observed load capacity and deflections.

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REFERENCES

- American Concrete Institute (2007). Report on Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Reinforcement for Concrete Structures. (ACI 440R-07:2007)
- American Standard Test Method. (2017). Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials. (ASTM D 3039/D 3039M-17)

- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2017). Concreto autoadensável - Parte 1: Classificação, controle e recebimento no estado fresco. (ABNT NBR 15823:2017).
- Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas. (2018). Concreto - Ensaio de compressão de corpos de prova cilíndricos. (ABNT NBR 5739:2018).
- Cardoso, M. G. (2020). Contribuições para dosagem de concretos autoadensáveis reforçados com fibras pelo método do empacotamento Compressível. [Master's thesis, Universidade de Brasília].
- European Standard (2004). Eurocode 4: Design of composite steel and concrete structures – Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings. (EN 1994-1-1).
- Fam, A., Nelson, M. (2012). New Bridge Deck Cast onto Corrugated GFRP Stay-in-Place Structural Forms with Interlocking Connections. *Journal of composites for construction, ASCE*. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0000229](http://dx.doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000229)
- Fang, H., Xu, X., Liu, W., Qi, Y., Bai, Y., Zhang, B., Hui, D. (2016). Flexural behavior of composite concrete slabs reinforced by FRP grid facesheets. *Composites Part B* 92 (46-62). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.02.029>
- Honickman, H. N. (2008). Pultruded GFRP sections as stay-in-place structural open formwork for concrete slabs and girders. [Master's thesis, Queen's University].
- He, J., Liu, Y., Chen, A., Dai, L. (2012). Experimental investigation of movable hybrid GFRP and concrete bridge deck. *Construction and Building Materials* 26 (49-64). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.05.002>
- Marinucci, G. (2019). *Materiais compósitos poliméricos: Fundamentos e tecnologia*. Artliber Editora.
- Mazumdar, S. K. (2002). *Composites manufacturing: materials, product, and process engineering*. CRC Press.
- Nelson, M., & Fam, A. (2013). Structural GFRP Permanent Forms with T-Shape Ribs for Bridge Decks Supported by Precast Concrete Girders. *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, Vol. 18, No. 9. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0000418](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0000418)
- Nelson, M., & Fam, A. (2014). Full bridge testing at scale constructed with novel FRP stay-in-place structural forms for concrete deck. *Construction and Building Materials* 50, 368-376. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.09.056>
- Pereira, E. V. (2017). *Influência de Fibras de Aço no Comportamento Mecânico e nos Mecanismos de Fissuração de Concretos Autoadensáveis*. [Master's thesis, Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro].
- Pournasiri, E., Pham, T. M., & Hao, H. (2022). Behavior of ultrahigh-performance concrete bridge decks with new Y-shape FRP stay-in-place formworks. *Journal of Composites for Construction* 26 (3): 04022023. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0001214](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0001214)
- Siwowski, T., Rajchel, M. (2019). Structural performance of a hybrid FRP composite – lightweight concrete bridge girder. *Composites Part B* (174). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107055>
- Silva, J. F. F. (2020). *Avaliação experimental sobre o comportamento mecânico de conectores de cisalhamento do tipo perfofrp em paredes pré-moldadas de concreto com isolamento incorporado*. [Master's thesis, Universidade de Brasília].
- Souza, L. S., Lameiras, R. M. (2023). Projeto de Dimensionamento de Lajes Mistas de Concreto com Fôrmas Permanentes de PRFV. XIV Congresso Brasileiro de Pontes e Estruturas - CBPE, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.
- Tian, J. Wu, X., Zheng, Y., Du, Y., Quan, X. (2018). Experimental Study and Mixed-Dimensional FE Analysis of T-Rib GFRP Plate-Concrete Composite Bridge Decks. *Hindawi: Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7531912>

Zoghi, M. (2014). *The international handbook of FRP composites in civil engineering*. CRC Press.

Zuo, Y., Mosallam, A., Xin, H., Liu, Y., He, J. (2018). Flexural performance of a hybrid GFRP-concrete bridge deck with composite T-shaped perforated rib connectors. *Composite Structures* (194), 263-278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.03.105>